

THE ROLE OF PRAGMATIC ASSESSMENT IN EVALUATING DISCOURSE COMPETENCE IN HIGH SCHOOL LEARNERS

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***Abstract.** Pragmatic competence has become, especially in the last few decades, one of the issues that has attracted attention in the field as an integral part of language competence. The realization that good command of linguistic knowledge in the target language will not be enough to master the language has generated the need to study the value and impact of pragmatic competence in language education. This review aims to provide a brief overview of pragmatics and pragmatic competence, the pedagogical significance of pragmatic competence, highlighting the relevant theoretical components of pragmatics. For the purposes of this review, the relevant literature covering the definitions of pragmatics and pragmatic competence as well as the research conducted in the field of pragmatic competence is presented.*

***Keywords.** Pragmatic competence, foreign language education, communicative competence, teaching pragmatics.*

Communication is a part of any social life in which people feel the need to interact with each other for specific reasons. It is through the concept of language that people can communicate with a variety of interlocutors in a variety of settings. However, when interacting, people must follow things that go beyond words. They must know how to say something, as well as when, where and to whom to say it. Thus, communication is much more than just arranging some words in a linear order to form a set of elements. Language users are expected to follow some conventions according to which their conversation will not only be meaningful but also appropriate. This analysis of how to say things in appropriate ways and places is mainly called pragmatics. It is known that the communicative method occupies a

leading place in the theory and practice of teaching foreign languages in a language university and is aimed at the formation of communicative competence.

In scientific and methodological literature, there is a variety of positions regarding the definition of this term and its content, and although most researchers agree on the multi-component nature of this type of competence, their ideas about which of its components are dominant differ significantly. Among the key ones, authors include linguistic, speech or, in the terms of some authors, pragmatic and socio-cultural or sociolinguistic competences. A number of researchers expand the content of competence by highlighting discursive, thematic, social, compensatory and educational components. In documents developed by the Council of Europe, the linguistic, socio-cultural and pragmatic aspects of communicative competence are highlighted as the most significant.

The fact of the presence of a pragmatic component in the structure of communicative competence is undoubtedly important. However, it should be noted that some scientists express the opinion that the concept of "pragmatic" can be used as a synonym for the word "communicative", since the impact on the addressee is of primary importance. In our opinion, the broadest concept is communication, in other words, the concept of pragmatics overlaps with the concept of communication. However, this does not call into question the legitimacy of the simultaneous existence of these terms. In this regard, the point of view of M. Kroski, who singles out the function of influence among the functions of the communicative process, that is, changing the ideas, concepts and attitudes of the communication partner, deserves attention. This is confirmed by the point of view of Yu. S. Stepanov, who defines pragmatics as a system of means and techniques used by the author to achieve his goals and "for the best impact on the listener in order to convince him, excite him, etc." Considering these provisions through the prism of linguodidactics, it becomes obvious that there is no basis for doubts about the need to distinguish pragmatic competence along with communicative competence.

Pragmatic competence can and should be developed through explicit and implicit instruction, with the former predominating, using a range of activities and situations/contexts. Particular attention should be paid to the rules of social norms that differ from those in the learners' native cultures. After all, communication is not just about exchanging messages, it is also about correctly and appropriately interpreting the intentions of both parties and being able to respond accordingly. This is why integrating elements of pragmatic competence into EFL curricula and lesson plans is crucial.

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